

Integrative therapeutic strategies in chronic kidney disease: from precision to regeneration

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Academic Editor: Nemanja Rančić

Abstract

Chronic kidney disease (CKD) affects over 850 million individuals globally, largely driven by aging, diabetes, and hypertension. Current therapeutic strategies primarily focus on renal replacement and symptom management, with limited capacity for prevention or tissue regeneration. This review addresses the urgent need for integrative, individualized frameworks in CKD management, encompassing precision medicine, regenerative therapies, multidisciplinary care (MDC), and nutraceutical interventions. We conducted a narrative synthesis of the recent literature across four domains: (1) precision medicine utilizing omics-based biomarkers (e.g., suPAR, Col5a1) for early detection and stratified risk profiling; (2) regenerative strategies including mesenchymal stem cells, induced pluripotent stem cells, and bioengineered tissues, which show anti-inflammatory and nephroprotective effects; (3) MDC models integrating nephrologists, nurses, dietitians, and social workers, which are linked to improved outcomes in mortality, dialysis initiation, and hospitalizations; and (4) emerging nutraceuticals derived from culinary spices (e.g., curcumin, allicin, flavonoids, capsaicin), which demonstrate antioxidative, anti-inflammatory, and antifibrotic activity, including modulation of the gut–kidney axis. Preliminary studies indicate that combining these strategies may yield synergistic benefits: biomarkers enhance targeting, MDC improves adherence and coordination, and bioactives offer molecular-level modulation. Early-phase trials report improvements in estimated glomerular filtration rate (eGFR), systemic inflammation, patient adherence, and cost-efficiency. Additionally, representative genetic panels, such as COL4A3–5, NPHS1/2, WT1, PKD1/2, UMOD, HNF1B, APOL1, and complement-related genes (e.g., CFH, C3), are increasingly used in CKD phenotyping. Their clinical utility spans early diagnosis, prognostication, familial risk assessment, and therapeutic stratification across glomerular, cystic, tubulointerstitial, syndromic, and APOL1-associated nephropathies. Integrative, personalized therapies promote proactive, reparative, and sustainable CKD management.

Keywords: *chronic kidney disease, precision medicine, stem cell therapy, integrated care, regenerative medicine*

Citation: Sánchez-González DJ, Trejo-Bahena NI, Méndez-Bolaina E, Ramírez-Sánchez I, Herrera-Cogco EdIC, Gutiérrez-Salmeán G. Integrative therapeutic strategies in chronic kidney disease: from precision to regeneration. *Academia Medicine and Health* 2025;2. <https://doi.org/10.20935/AcadMedHealth8045>

1. Introduction

Chronic kidney disease (CKD) is a progressive, multifactorial condition characterized by the gradual deterioration of renal function. Histopathologically, it involves structural changes such as glomerulosclerosis, tubular atrophy, and interstitial fibrosis, which are frequently observed in kidney biopsies of affected individuals [1–3]. As CKD advances toward its terminal stages, renal fibrosis becomes more pronounced due to persistent inflammation and inadequate tissue repair mechanisms [4]. Globally, CKD affects more than 850 million individuals, and its prevalence is increasing steadily due to the rising burden of aging, diabetes, and hypertension [1–3].

CKD arises from a multifactorial interplay of medical and environmental contributors. Major underlying conditions include diabetes mellitus, systemic hypertension, and cardiovascular disease, especially atherosclerotic renal vascular disease, which may cause ischemic nephropathy and secondary hypertension. In glomerular

diseases, such as IgA nephropathy and focal segmental glomerulosclerosis, proteinuria and histological activity guide treatment decisions. Environmental and occupational factors, such as chronic exposure to nephrotoxic drugs, heavy labor in hot climates, and alcohol-related metabolic stress, may also predispose individuals to CKD progression [1–4]. Glomerulonephritis, principally IgA nephropathy and focal segmental glomerulosclerosis (FSGS), also contributes significantly to CKD. In these conditions, disease activity is commonly defined by proteinuria levels, and management strategies rely on genetic background and histologic findings rather than on established biomarker-guided protocols [4].

CKD is stratified into five stages based on the estimated glomerular filtration rate (eGFR), reflecting the kidney's capacity to filter fluids through nephrons over time. In Stage 1, kidney damage exists despite normal function; Stage 2 shows mild decline with few

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symptoms; Stage 3 presents moderate impairment and early clinical manifestations; Stage 4 involves severe dysfunction, often requiring pre-dialysis planning; and Stage 5, or end-stage kidney disease (ESKD), necessitates dialysis or transplantation [5]. Diagnosis typically involves evidence of kidney damage for over three months alongside an eGFR that is compatible with at least Stage 3 [2–5].

Symptoms vary with disease stage and etiology, ranging from fatigue, edema, and hypertension to altered urination patterns. Importantly, early stages can be asymptomatic, complicating timely detection in the absence of regular screening [5, 6]. If left untreated, CKD often progresses to kidney failure, with life-threatening systemic complications [5]. In addition to obesity [7, 8], genetic predispositions and other underlying medical conditions are also risk factors for CKD [6]. Understanding these predisposing factors is essential for early diagnosis and effective management to prevent further renal damage [5].

CKD management requires a multifaceted strategy, encompassing pharmacological interventions, lifestyle modification, dietary regulation, and, increasingly, integrative therapeutic models. These approaches aim not only to slow disease progression but also to improve patient quality of life. Multidisciplinary care (MDC), involving nephrologists, dietitians, nurses, and social workers, plays a vital role in optimizing clinical outcomes and supporting patients across the disease continuum [6].

Despite advances in standard care, current strategies remain predominantly reactive, focusing on slowing progression or replacing function via dialysis or transplantation. However, a shift is underway toward early molecular diagnosis and biologically restorative interventions. In this regard, bone marrow-derived mesenchymal stem cells (MSCs) have shown substantial renoprotective effects in preclinical models of diabetic nephropathy, reducing inflammation, apoptosis, and fibrosis through multiple molecular pathways [9, 10].

This review evaluates four pillars of this emerging integrative paradigm: precision medicine, regenerative therapies, MDC frameworks, and nutraceutical interventions involving bioactive dietary compounds. CKD imposes considerable economic and clinical burdens, including cardiovascular and metabolic complications [7, 8]. Traditional approaches, such as renin–angiotensin system (RAS) blockade and late-stage dialysis, fail to address the underlying pathophysiology of nephron loss and fibrotic remodeling, nor do they promote renal repair [11].

Advances in precision medicine now enable stratified patient care. Biomarkers such as gene-encoding Collagen Type V Alpha 1 Chain (Col5a1), Neutrophil Gelatinase-Associated Lipocalin (NGAL), and soluble urokinase-type plasminogen activator receptor (suPAR) facilitate early detection and allow for targeted therapy in high-risk individuals [12, 13]. Concurrently, regenerative modalities including mesenchymal stem/stromal cells (MSCs), induced pluripotent stem cells (iPSCs) [14], and kidney organoids have demonstrated therapeutic potential through mechanisms involving immunomodulation, angiogenesis, and tubular repair [15, 16]. This is supported by the NEPHSTROM trial, a first-in-human, multicenter, randomized, placebo-controlled Phase 1b/2a study that evaluated the safety, tolerability, and preliminary efficacy of allogeneic, CD362-selected mesenchymal stromal cells (ORBCELM) in adults with type 2 diabetes mellitus and progressive diabetic kidney disease [17].

The structured implementation of these innovations is supported by MDC, which integrates clinical, nutritional, pharmaceutical, and psychosocial dimensions. When applied early, MDC is associated with improved survival and delayed renal replacement therapy [18]. Moreover, MDC is essential for the safe and effective delivery of complex interventions such as cell-based therapy and biomarker-guided pharmacological regimens.

Crucially, these modalities are not isolated but complementary. Biomarkers guide candidate selection for biologics, regenerative therapies restore function at the cellular level, and MDC sustains patient engagement, safety monitoring, and therapy adherence. Pilot trials integrating these strategies, including omics-based diagnostics, MSC infusion, and telemonitoring, have demonstrated benefits such as eGFR stabilization and reduced hospitalizations [13, 17].

This review synthesizes the current landscape of these converging approaches and proposes a clinically actionable framework. By aligning molecular diagnostics, biological repair, and team-based care, CKD management can evolve from reactive maintenance to proactive and personalized renal health.

2. Materials and methods

This review constitutes a narrative literature review, designed to integrate evidence across multidisciplinary domains that are relevant to CKD. The synthesis aimed to provide a conceptual overview rather than a systematic or scoping analysis [19]. A structured search strategy was developed and executed across four major electronic databases: PubMed, Scopus, Web of Science, and Embase. The search included both Medical Subject Headings (MeSHs) and free-text terms related to CKD, precision medicine, biomarkers, stem cell therapy, regenerative medicine, multidisciplinary care, integrated care models, and renal replacement therapy. The literature search was restricted to publications from January 2007 to November 2025 to encompass both foundational and contemporary developments. Eligible documents included peer-reviewed original research articles, systematic reviews, meta-analyses, and clinical guidelines that addressed human or animal models and were relevant to the integrative strategies discussed. Exclusion criteria comprised commentaries, editorials, and conference abstracts without accessible full texts [19].

A critical narrative analysis was conducted to synthesize key findings, evaluate methodological rigor, identify research gaps, and highlight future investigative directions, in alignment with best practices for literature-based scientific assessments [19]. Data were thematically categorized, and all references were systematically organized using Zotero to ensure precision and conformity with journal-specific citation formats.

Study selection was performed by two independent reviewers, who first screened the titles and abstracts, followed by full-text reviews to determine final inclusion. Any disagreements were resolved through discussion and consensus. Data extracted from the included studies encompassed study design, sample size, CKD stage, type of intervention (such as the specific stem cell or care model applied), key clinical outcomes (including changes in estimated glomerular filtration rate, mortality, and quality of life), and relevant biomarkers used for diagnostic or monitoring purposes.

A narrative synthesis approach was adopted to organize the evidence into four thematic domains, aligned with the scope of this review: precision diagnostics, regenerative therapies, multidisciplinary care models, and adjunctive nutraceutical strategies. Comparative analyses were conducted qualitatively across studies within each domain. Given the heterogeneous and early-stage nature of many therapeutic strategies discussed, a formal GRADE assessment was not applicable. Instead, we present a narrative stratification of interventions based on their current level of evidence [20].

Because this work is based entirely on previously published peer-reviewed research, no ethical approval was required. All included studies were examined for compliance with ethical standards and scientific rigor.

The aim of this review is to synthesize and critically evaluate current integrative therapeutic strategies for CKD, emphasizing their potential convergence into a unified framework for personalized, reparative, and sustainable care. Specifically, this review seeks to describe recent developments in omics-guided diagnostics and biomarker-based precision medicine; assess preclinical and clinical data on regenerative interventions such as MSCs, iPSCs and bioengineered renal constructs; and evaluate the impact of multidisciplinary care models on patient outcomes, including estimated glomerular filtration rate preservation, dialysis initiation, and health system sustainability [21]. Additionally, this review explores the emerging role of bioactive phytochemicals from culinary spices, such as curcumin, allicin, flavonoids, and capsaicin, as molecularly targeted adjunctive agents acting on inflammatory, fibrotic, oxidative, and gut–renal pathways.

Finally, this review identifies gaps in the current evidence base and outlines key priorities for future research, including the need for scalable, cost-effective, and digitally supported models of care that integrate precision diagnostics, biologic therapies, dietary interventions, and coordinated multidisciplinary support.

3. Precision medicine in chronic kidney disease

CKD poses a major global health burden, affecting approximately 9–10% of the adult population and contributing significantly to morbidity, mortality, and healthcare expenditures [22]. Traditional risk stratification in CKD relies on eGFR and albuminuria,

which remain the major parameters used for monitoring outcomes and guiding interventions (e.g., albuminuria < 0.5 g/24 h in IgA nephropathy). Although cystatin C can provide complementary information in specific settings, it has not yet been widely adopted for following eGFR trajectories in adults with CKD [22–27]. Precision medicine, empowered by advances in genomics, proteomics, metabolomics, and artificial intelligence (AI), offers novel tools to improve prediction, prevention, and tailored therapeutic strategies in CKD [23]. To enhance clarity and distinguish levels of evidence, the following subsections highlight preclinical, observational, and computational modeling studies that are relevant to precision medicine.

3.1. Molecular and genetic biomarkers and omics integration

High-throughput omics platforms have facilitated the identification of novel biomarkers that surpass conventional measures in terms of sensitivity and specificity. Cystatin C, for instance, has been shown to outperform serum creatinine in eGFR and predicting progression to ESKD, especially in diverse populations [22, 24, 25]. In parallel, neutrophil gelatinase-associated lipocalin (NGAL) has gained recognition as an early marker of tubular injury, validated for acute kidney injury and increasingly investigated in CKD settings [26]. However, its disease specificity is limited, as NGAL levels are elevated in a wide range of inflammatory conditions, reducing its reliability for CKD-specific applications. Kidney Injury Molecule-1 (KIM-1), although showing promise in early research, has not yet achieved widespread clinical adoption for routine CKD diagnostics. Other proposed markers include COL5a1 and suPAR, but these are not currently recommended for use in glomerular diseases such as FSGS. In fact, diagnostic approaches to FSGS and minimal change disease are shifting toward identification of autoimmune mechanisms and circulating antibodies against nephrin and podocin. Uromodulin, particularly in serum form, is also being explored as a marker of tubular health, although its diagnostic utility remains under investigation. These limitations underscore the need for further validation of biomarker-based strategies before routine integration into personalized CKD care [13]. In line with updated KDIGO and NKF recommendations and the forthcoming consensus report (JASN, 2025) [25], genetic testing is increasingly recognized as a core component of precision nephrology across CKD phenotypes. **Table 1** summarizes representative genetic markers that are currently relevant to clinical decision-making [25].

Table 1 • Genetic Testing in the Management of Adult CKD: Representative Phenotypes and Key Genes. Representative recommended CKD phenotypes and associated genes for diagnostic genetic testing, based on recent KDIGO and NKF guidelines. These associations support clinical utility in diagnosis, prognosis, and therapeutic stratification. Adapted from JASN (2025) and KDIGO/NKF guidelines [25].

CKD phenotype	Representative genes/panels	Clinical and diagnostic implications
Glomerular disease of unknown etiology	<i>COL4A3, COL4A4, COL4A5, NPHS1, NPHS2, WT1, INF2</i>	Clarifies diagnosis in familial or atypical glomerulopathies; differentiates between Alport spectrum, FSGS, and nephrotic syndromes
Cystic kidney disease	<i>PKD1, PKD2, GANAB, DNAJB11, IFT140</i>	Confirms autosomal dominant or recessive PKD; informs prognosis and family screening
Tubulointerstitial or metabolic disorders	<i>UMOD, MUC1, REN, SLC34A1, CLCN5, OCRL, CTNS</i>	Identifies monogenic tubular defects; informs personalized electrolyte and metabolic management
CKD with extrarenal or syndromic features	<i>HNF1B, LMX1B, COQ8B, NEK8, MITOCHONDRIAL DNA</i>	Enables early detection of syndromic CKD; guides multidisciplinary evaluation (e.g., hepatic, ocular, neurologic)
CKD of African ancestry/APOL1-associated nephropathy	<i>APOL1</i> (G1, G2 alleles)	Risk stratification for hypertension-associated CKD and transplantation suitability
Complement-mediated kidney disease	<i>CFH, CFI, C3, MCP, DGKE</i>	Aids differential diagnosis and treatment guidance for atypical hemolytic uremic syndrome or C3 glomerulopathy

3.2. Computational models and integrative approaches

Integrative multi-omics in CKD combines genomics, epigenomics, transcriptomics, proteomics, metabolomics and lipidomics, microbiome and metagenomics, exposome, immunomics, phenome and digital data, and single-cell and spatial profiles to enable finer patient stratification and more precise sub-phenotyping [18, 21]. Phenome and digital refers to high-dimensional non-molecular data, including structured clinical phenotypes from EHRs (electronic health records), wearable signals, and computable features from digital pathology and radiology. Single-cell and spatial captures cell-resolved and tissue-mapped profiles such as scRNA-seq (single-cell RNA sequencing), scATAC-seq (single-cell assay for transposase-accessible chromatin sequencing), multi-ome (joint scRNA-seq plus scATAC-seq from the same cell), and CITE-seq (cellular indexing of transcriptomes and epitopes by sequencing), together with spatial transcriptomics, proteomics, and metabolomics, to localize states and interactions. Exposome denotes the lifetime landscape of external exposures and internal biological responses, linking environment and lifestyle to CKD risk and progression [18, 21, 23].

One notable example is the Omics-Driven Machine Learning (ODML) model, which combines these layers with AI-based algorithms to improve predictive accuracy and cost-effectiveness, outperforming standard statistical models. However, while AI-driven tools like ODML show promise, their clinical utility remains under evaluation. Current pediatric applications do not necessarily translate to adult CKD, and their generalizability requires further validation across diverse cohorts. Similarly, enhanced microscopy, although valuable as a research tool, has not yet established a definitive role in routine diagnostic nephropathology [23, 26] (Figure 1).

3.3. Challenges in AI validation and implementation for CKD prediction

While AI-driven tools like ODML models show improved predictive accuracy for CKD, several challenges remain for clinical adoption. Validating these models requires robust, longitudinal datasets with well-curated clinical records, biomarker profiles, treatment histories, and outcome data. Many existing models are trained on data from limited populations, which affects their generalizability to broader clinical settings. Furthermore, regulatory frameworks for AI in healthcare are still evolving, and standards for algorithm transparency, clinical validation, and real-world performance monitoring must be established to ensure safe and effective integration into CKD care [23, 26–31].

3.4. Artificial intelligence and predictive modeling

AI, particularly through machine learning (ML) and deep learning (DL), offers powerful capabilities for prognostic modeling by capturing complex, nonlinear relationships within high-dimensional datasets. A dynamic kidney failure prediction model (KFDeep), trained on nearly 4600 patient records and externally validated, demonstrated strong predictive performance (AUROC 0.946 internally; 0.805 externally), outperforming conventional models [18, 27]. Other ensemble-based models using algorithms like CatBoost (Category Boosting) have achieved excellent diagnostic precision (AUC > 0.99) for early-stage CKD detection, even in low-resource environments [28].

Explainable AI methods such as SHAP (SHapley Additive exPlanations) values [29] have been instrumental in visualizing

how individual features (e.g., hemoglobin levels, albuminuria, glycemic status) contribute to risk predictions, fostering greater clinician trust and interpretability in automated decision-support tools [15, 30].

Figure 1 • CKD multi-omics: high dimensional datasets. Centric chart summarizing an integrated multi-omics and digital pathology framework for CKD. High-dimensional data from genomics, epigenomics, transcriptomics, proteomics, metabolomics and lipidomics, and the microbiome or metagenome, together with the exposome, immunomics, phenome and digital sources, and single-cell and spatial readouts, are represented and fused with machine learning to reveal mechanisms, therapeutic targets, and genotype–phenotype links from biopsies using computational whole slide imaging. This approach enables discovery of prognostic and predictive biomarkers, risk stratification, assessment of treatment response, and clinically interpretable reports for precision nephrology [18, 21–23].

3.5. Clinical applications and impact

Precision medicine in CKD has several promising clinical applications: early diagnosis and risk stratification allow for the timely identification of high-risk individuals, enabling the initiation of nephroprotective measures; pharmacogenomic tailoring using genetic markers (e.g., APOL1, UMOD variants) and predictive models can inform drug selection, dosing, and timing [31, 32]; and targeted trials in biomarker-defined subgroups enable more focused enrollment in clinical trials for novel therapies, such as Sodium-Glucose Co-Transporter 2 (SGLT2) inhibitors or endothelin receptor antagonists, thereby enhancing trial efficiency and outcome relevance [33]. In certain glomerular diseases, particularly FSGS, the detection of podocyte or basement-membrane gene mutations via renal biopsy or genetic testing has prognostic and therapeutic implications. Evidence suggests that when such mutations are present, the disease is less likely to respond to immunosuppressive therapies (such as steroids or cytotoxic agents), and therefore primary management may focus on RAS blockade (with or without SGLT2 inhibitors) rather than aggressive immunomodulation [1–4, 8–10].

Despite these advances, several challenges persist. Data heterogeneity

across healthcare systems and omics platforms underscores the urgent need for harmonized standards to enable meaningful data integration and reproducibility [15, 34, 35]. Algorithmic bias remains a concern, as models that have been trained in one population may underperform in external cohorts, highlighting the critical importance of rigorous external validation [36]. Ethical and regulatory frameworks must also keep pace, ensuring data privacy, transparent algorithm design, and compliance with legislation such as the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR), a comprehensive data protection law enacted by the European Union, which has been effective since May 2018 [21].

Integrated evidence from precision medicine frameworks has enabled targeted trial design in biomarker-defined CKD subgroups. Notably, clinical trials such as DAPA-CKD and CANVAS have demonstrated the efficacy of SGLT2 inhibitors in high-risk patients identified through molecular phenotyping, explored in biomarker-based stratification studies [37]. Additionally, emerging models like Omics-Driven Machine Learning underscore the potential of lipid proteomics and molecular biomarkers in guiding future precision-driven CKD trials [21].

3.6. Pharmacologic advances in CKD and cardiorenal syndrome management

Recent therapeutic advances have significantly shaped the management of CKD and cardiorenal syndromes. RAS blockade remains a cornerstone of treatment, due to its proven efficacy in reducing glomerular hypertension and mitigating angiotensin II-mediated inflammation and fibrosis. Additionally, SGLT2 inhibitors have shown robust renoprotective and cardioprotective effects, independently of glycemic control. In patients with obesity with or without diabetes, GLP-1 receptor agonists or dual GIP/GLP-1 agonists further support metabolic and renal outcomes. The role of mineralocorticoid receptor antagonists (MRAs), particularly non-steroidal agents such as finerenone, has expanded in both diabetic and non-diabetic CKD, offering anti-inflammatory and antifibrotic benefits. These therapies represent a paradigm shift in CKD management and address both hemodynamic and molecular drivers of disease progression [8–12].

4. Mitochondria-targeted antioxidant therapy: a precision strategy for CKD in the context of obesity and aging

Obesity is a well-established risk factor for the development and progression of CKD, particularly when accompanied by comorbidities such as diabetes or when secondary FSGS is present. Several pathophysiological mechanisms have been proposed, including glomerular hyperfiltration, podocyte injury, and renal hemodynamic alterations. However, isolated glomerular enlargement due to obesity does not necessarily lead to CKD progression without additional risk factors. In parallel, obesity may induce lipotoxicity, ectopic lipid accumulation, and low-grade chronic inflammation through the release of proinflammatory cytokines from adipose tissue, which may contribute to mitochondrial dysfunction and potentially compromise renal function, although this remains under investigation [38–42].

A comprehensive meta-analysis involving over 3.5 million individuals across 21 studies and a mean follow-up of 9.86 years demonstrated that individuals with obesity have a 1.81-fold increased risk of developing CKD compared to counterparts without

obesity [38]. The pathogenic mechanisms are both indirect and direct: Indirectly, it promotes the development of diabetes mellitus and systemic arterial hypertension, both recognized as causes of the development of CKD [33]. Directly, it leads to glomerular hyperfiltration, renal hemodynamic alterations, podocyte stress and damage, and dysregulation of gene expression, including downregulation of *Sirt1* and adiponectin, which further compromise podocyte integrity [39]. In addition, lipotoxicity, ectopic lipid accumulation, and chronic inflammation are generated through the release of proinflammatory cytokines from adipose tissue, which disrupt normal kidney function [40].

In parallel, aging constitutes a significant non-modifiable risk factor. Age-related renal changes include glomerulosclerosis, tubular atrophy, arteriosclerosis, and interstitial fibrosis, which lead to a progressive decline in GFR, estimated to decrease by approximately 8 mL/min per decade after the age of 30, thereby predisposing the elderly population to CKD development [41].

A key shared pathogenic denominator between obesity, aging, and CKD is mitochondrial dysfunction. Obesity induces a chronic proinflammatory state characterized by excessive generation of reactive oxygen species (ROS), which exacerbates oxidative stress and disrupts mitochondrial homeostasis. Aging further contributes through the accumulation of mitochondrial DNA (mtDNA) mutations, impaired oxidative phosphorylation, and diminished expression of antioxidant defense enzymes, all of which increase mitochondrial ROS generation and functional deterioration [42]. These alterations cause mitochondrial fragmentation, membrane depolarization, and a self-perpetuating cycle of oxidative damage. Given the high metabolic activity of renal tissue and its dependency on mitochondrial ATP production, mitochondrial integrity is critical to nephron survival and function. Several studies have implicated mitochondrial dysfunction in the pathogenesis and progression of CKD, reinforcing the rationale for targeting mitochondria as a therapeutic strategy [43].

To structure the evidence clearly, the following section focuses first on mechanistic/preclinical data and then on translational therapeutic candidates. With CKD projected to become the fifth leading cause of death globally by 2040 [2], there is an urgent need to explore and implement novel interventions. Mitochondria-targeted antioxidants such as MitoQ, Mito-TEMPO, and astaxanthin have shown promising renoprotective effects in preclinical models [44–46].

These agents exert multi-faceted actions, including mitigation of oxidative damage, restoration of mitochondrial dynamics, inhibition of apoptosis, and preservation of renal structure and function [47]. Their therapeutic potential is summarized in **Table 2**.

4.1. Limitations and translational barriers

Most data on mitochondria-targeted antioxidants such as MitoQ and Mito-TEMPO are derived from animal models. Human trials are limited and often underpowered, with some failing to replicate preclinical benefits. Safety profiles are still being established, and bioavailability remains a major limitation to their clinical translation [44–46]. While mitochondrial dysfunction is a plausible contributor to CKD pathophysiology, especially in the context of metabolic stressors such as obesity and aging, the current evidence remains largely preclinical and associative. Mitochondrial mechanisms are proposed contributors rather than established causal pathways of CKD [42–47].

Table 2 • Mitochondria-targeted antioxidants in CKD: preclinical evidence. Mitochondria-targeted antioxidants in experimental models of CKD. Summary of key mitochondria-targeted antioxidants evaluated in animal and cellular models of CKD. The table outlines the experimental models employed, the observed mechanisms of action, and the therapeutic effects reported. This preclinical evidence supports the potential of mitochondria-directed therapies as an innovative strategy to mitigate CKD progression associated with oxidative stress, aging, and obesity. Data adapted from multiple sources [44–47].

Antioxidant	Model	Effect
MitoQ	Diabetic mice, rat and porcine kidneys	Reverses mitochondrial dysfunction, enhances mitophagy, reduces mitochondrial reactive oxygen species, inhibits apoptosis, and protects against renal tubular injury
Mito-TEMPO	C57BL/6J mice	Alleviates mitochondrial dysfunction; improves renal function; reduces mitochondrial reactive oxygen species; inhibits NLRP3 inflammasome; and has antifibrotic effects
Astaxanthin	Human renal mesangial cells (HRMCs) and diabetic mice	Reduces mitochondrial reactive oxygen species and protects against kidney damage

5. Bioactive phytochemicals from culinary spices: emerging nutritional strategies in CKD management

This section examines the potential of nutraceutical and dietary-derived bioactive compounds as adjunctive strategies in CKD management. Within the MDC framework, nutritional therapy plays a pivotal role not only in managing classical complications of CKD, including hyperkalemia, hyperphosphatemia, altered bone mineral metabolism, fluid overload, and protein-energy wasting, but also in improving hard clinical outcomes such as disease progression, morbidity, mortality, and quality of life, once renal replacement therapy (RRT) begins [48, 49].

Conventionally, the role of dietitians includes calculating hypercaloric diet plans and adjusting protein intake based on disease stage—low protein in pre-RRT and higher protein during RRT—along with the regulation of sodium, potassium, and phosphorus, according to biochemical parameters and symptoms [50]. However, it is now well documented that pattern-based nutritional approaches, rather than single-nutrient strategies, better capture the synergistic effects of habitual food combinations over time, and these benefits are further complemented by moderate physical activity tailored to age and functional status, particularly structured walking programs. Recent evidence indicates that even low-intensity routines, such as accumulating approximately 7000–12,000 walking steps per day, are associated with better health-related quality of life in patients with CKD, supporting the incorporation of simple walking prescriptions into routine CKD care alongside comprehensive dietary interventions [51].

Epidemiological and observational evidence consistently shows that Western dietary patterns, which are high in fats, added sugars, and sodium but low in fiber, are associated with increased risk and progression of CKD. Conversely, the Mediterranean, Nordic, anti-inflammatory, and DASH (Dietary Approaches to Stop Hypertension) diets have been linked to improved kidney function, reduced proteinuria and oxidative stress, mitigation of metabolic disturbances and muscle loss, decreased mortality, and delayed need for RRT [52–54]. Within these dietary patterns, and others such as the Milpa and Turkish diets, spices are not only flavor enhancers but also sources of bioactive compounds that beneficially modulate key pathophysiological pathways in CKD (e.g., endothelial function; inflammation and fibrosis; the Renin–Angiotensin–Aldosterone System [RAAS]; the gut–kidney axis; and glucose and lipid homeostasis) [55].

5.1. Preclinical and clinical evidence of selected phytochemicals

Curcumin, the principal curcuminoid found in *Curcuma longa* (turmeric), exerts well-known anti-inflammatory effects through the binding and modulation of Peroxisome Proliferator-Activated Receptor Gamma (PPAR- γ), a nuclear hormone receptor that plays a crucial role in regulating glucose metabolism, lipid storage, inflammation, and cellular differentiation. Randomized controlled trials (RCTs) in both non-dialysis and dialysis patients have shown that curcumin supplementation significantly reduces uremic toxins (e.g., indoxyl sulfate, p-cresyl sulfate), lipid peroxidation (malondialdehyde), and inflammatory mediators (TNF- α , CCL, IFN- γ , IL-4, IL-6), while promoting favorable microbial shifts [56].

Flavonoids, polyphenolic compounds that are present in herbs such as parsley, rosemary, thyme, and oregano also exhibit antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, and endothelially protective properties. These compounds are supported by experimental and limited clinical data suggesting benefits in glucose metabolism and endothelial function, thereby reducing hyperglycemia, glomerulosclerosis, and renal fibrosis and potentially attenuating CKD progression [57].

Allicin, a sulfur-containing compound in garlic, is recognized for its antimicrobial, immunomodulatory, and cardioprotective effects. Preclinical studies in nephrectomy and diabetic nephropathy models show that allicin improves systolic blood pressure, albuminuria, nephrin expression, antioxidant enzyme activity, and endothelial nitric oxide synthase (eNOS) levels. Furthermore, it interacts with Angiotensin II Type 1 Receptor (AT1R), similarly to drugs like losartan, reduces creatinine and BUN levels, and attenuates the MAPK and NF- κ B pathways. An observational human study found a 30% lower risk of CKD among those consuming higher levels of allium vegetables [58, 59].

Cinnamon and saffron, widely used in Middle Eastern cuisines, contain bioactive compounds (e.g., cinnamaldehyde, cinnamic acid, crocin, safranal) that act as potent antioxidants and anti-inflammatory agents. These compounds improve glycemic and lipid profiles through mechanisms such as AMP-Activated Protein Kinase (AMPK) activation and β -cell regeneration. Early clinical data suggest potential glycemic and lipid improvements in CKD [60, 61].

The Milpa diet, a traditional Mexican eating pattern, features *Capsicum annuum* (chili pepper), which is rich in capsaicin,

a vanilloid alkaloid that activates Transient Receptor Potential Vanilloid 1 (TRPV1) [55]. Chronic activation leads to desensitization and anti-inflammatory effects. In experimental CKD, capsaicin reduced interstitial fibrosis and collagen accumulation; clinically, it has been used topically to relieve uremic pruritus, and dietary intake has been associated with nearly 50% reduced CKD risk [62].

In summary, bioactive compounds that are present in culinary spices demonstrate significant potential to modulate molecular mechanisms implicated in CKD [63]. Their integration into therapeutic dietary patterns, and possibly as standardized nutraceutical supplements, warrants consideration within MDC protocols.

5.2. Limitations, safety, and bioavailability challenges of nutraceuticals

Despite encouraging preclinical and emerging clinical evidence, nutraceutical interventions in CKD face important limitations that hinder their widespread application. A major concern is the lack of standardization in dosage, formulation, and delivery methods, complicating cross-study comparisons. Moreover, many trials report inconsistent or null clinical outcomes, and observational data are prone to confounding by concurrent dietary and lifestyle factors. Several commonly cited compounds such as curcumin, allicin, and capsaicin are also characterized by low oral bioavailability due to poor absorption, rapid metabolism, and low plasma stability, which restrict their therapeutic potential. Some compounds may interact adversely with medications or cause side effects at higher doses. Although small-scale studies suggest renoprotective effects, the current pool of randomized controlled trials remains limited in size, duration, and methodological rigor. Future research should prioritize large, well-designed trials using standardized formulations and dosing strategies to validate clinical efficacy and safety in CKD contexts [55–63]. It is important to emphasize that evidence of clinical efficacy in CKD is limited, and these compounds should not be interpreted as stand-alone treatments. Instead, they may complement established therapeutic approaches subject to rigorous future validation [49–63].

6. Regenerative therapies in CKD

CKD is characterized by irreversible nephron loss and progressive fibrosis, ultimately leading to ESKD. Although dialysis and transplantation remain the standard treatments, regenerative medicine offers the potential to restore renal structure and function. This section critically reviews recent preclinical and clinical advancements in stem cell-based and bioengineering approaches for renal regeneration [16, 64].

To improve clarity, this section is structured according to the type and level of evidence: preclinical findings, early-phase clinical trials, and advanced cell-based or tissue engineering strategies.

6.1. Preclinical developments in stem cell therapy

MSCs demonstrate renoprotective effects in various CKD animal models through paracrine anti-inflammatory, antifibrotic, and angiogenic mechanisms [16]. A comprehensive review concluded that MSCs modulate both fibrotic and immune pathways to promote renal repair, although outcomes vary depending on cell source and protocol differences [64]. Bioengineering strategies,

including decellularized kidney scaffolds and 3D bioprinting, have shown promise in reconstructing renal tissue architecture in animals, with ninety-nine studies evaluating decellularization and recellularization protocols, showing histological integration but also noting translational barriers [16, 64]. Renal progenitor and tubular epithelial cell therapies have likewise been explored [65]. CD133+ kidney-derived progenitor cells improved renal function and reduced fibrosis in 5/6 nephrectomy models, indicating activation of endogenous repair mechanisms [66].

6.2. Early-phase clinical trials of regenerative cell therapies

Transitioning from bench to bedside, several early-phase clinical trials have evaluated the safety and feasibility of MSCs and autologous CD34+ hematopoietic progenitor cells in patients with CKD. A small Phase 1 clinical study involving four patients with an eGFR of 15–28 mL/min/1.73 m² assessed the intra-arterial infusion of G-CSF-mobilized autologous CD34+ cells. The intervention demonstrated an improved eGFR slope (+0.22 ± 0.71 mL/min/1.73 m²/month), contrasting with the patients' pre-intervention decline (−1.36 ± 1.1), and reported a favorable safety profile [67]. In parallel, the NEPHSTROM Phase 1b/2a multicenter trial examined the intravenous administration of allogeneic CD362-enriched MSCs (ORBCEL M) in 16 adults with diabetic kidney disease. The results showed that the treatment was safe and associated with a slower decline in eGFR compared to placebo, although it did not significantly alter the measured GFR [17]. Moreover, a systematic review comprising 18 MSC-based trials across various CKD etiologies, including lupus nephritis and diabetic nephropathy, reported heterogeneous outcomes: while 7 trials showed eGFR stabilization or improvement, the remainder failed to demonstrate clinical benefit. This variability likely reflects differences in study design, cell dose, source (autologous vs. allogeneic), and delivery route [68]. Collectively, these studies confirm preliminary safety and feasibility, yet underscore the need for larger, well-powered Phase 2/3 trials to validate clinical efficacy.

6.3. Emerging advanced translational cell-based and tissue engineering strategies

Innovative approaches in regenerative nephrology continue to expand, including the use of iPSC-derived renal progenitors and organoids, which offer promising avenues for nephron replacement. Preclinical studies have demonstrated that iPSCs can differentiate into kidney-like structures forming tubular and glomerular elements both *in vitro* and after transplantation [65]. Similarly, Muse cells (multilineage-differentiating stress-enduring cells) have shown potential in murine models of CKD, integrating into damaged glomeruli and differentiating into podocytes, endothelial, and mesangial cells, ultimately contributing to improved renal function [69, 70]. Tissue-engineered scaffolds generated through decellularization and recellularization strategies have further enhanced renal architecture reconstruction, particularly when repopulated with progenitor or embryonic stem cell (ESC)-derived lineages [65]. Additionally, cell-free approaches, such as extracellular vesicles (EVs) derived from MSCs or iPSCs, exhibit beneficial paracrine effects, including modulation of inflammation and fibrosis, with advantages in storage, safety, and delivery, thereby representing a next-generation therapeutic modality in renal regeneration [71–73] (**Table 3**).

Table 3 • Overview of regenerative approaches for CKD: mechanisms and evidence. Regenerative therapies in CKD: summary of approaches, evidence, and clinical implications. All regenerative strategies aim to slow CKD progression, promote repair, or reduce reliance on replacement therapies. Despite safety in early-phase trials, efficacy validation in large-scale studies remains critical. Developed with reference to the manuscript's cited studies [16, 17, 63–72].

Regenerative strategy	Mechanism of action	Evidence base	Clinical implications
Mesenchymal Stem Cells (MSCs)	Paracrine effects: anti-inflammatory, antifibrotic, angiogenic	Preclinical CKD models show renoprotection; modulation of fibrosis and immune pathways	Improves glomerular structure, reduces oxidative stress
Decellularized kidney scaffolds	Biomimetic scaffolds enabling cell repopulation	99 studies evaluating integration and architecture in animal models	Reconstructs nephron units; translational barriers persist
CD133+ renal progenitor cells	Activation of endogenous repair	5/6 nephrectomy models show reduced fibrosis and improved function	Promising for early-stage interventions
Autologous CD34+ hematopoietic cells	Angiogenesis, nephron preservation	Phase 1 trial ($n = 4$) showed slowed eGFR decline	Safe and feasible; small sample size
Allogeneic CD362+ MSCs (ORBCEL M)	Anti-inflammatory, renoprotective	NEPHSTROM trial showed safety and slower eGFR decline	Needs further efficacy validation
iPSC-derived kidney organoids	Nephron-like structure generation	In vitro and in vivo integration; tubules and glomeruli formed	Long-term viability and function in vivo under study
Muse cells	Multilineage differentiation into renal cells	Murine CKD models show podocyte and endothelial regeneration	Functional recovery observed; translational studies needed
Extracellular Vesicles (EVs)	Cell-free delivery of regulatory miRNAs and proteins	Preclinical reduction in inflammation, fibrosis	Easier storage and delivery; favorable safety profile
Combined tissue engineering + ESC/iPSC	Enhanced recellularization	Synergistic effect with bioengineered scaffolds	Enables precision nephron replacement

6.4. Advancing regenerative strategies in CKD: from translational research to scalable therapies

Regenerative medicine in CKD explores stem cell therapies, tissue engineering, and cell-free methods like extracellular vesicles. These therapies aim to enhance kidney function and lessen reliance on dialysis or transplantation but are not yet substitutes for existing treatments in severe cases. Progressing these therapies necessitates standardization of global research protocols, conducting large clinical trials with validated endpoints, and combining regenerative approaches with scaffolds or antifibrotic agents for improved efficacy. Furthermore, promoting scalable cell-free therapies and implementing adaptive regulatory frameworks are vital for expediting clinical application, while ensuring equitable access and cost-effective delivery is critical for widespread adoption, especially in resource-constrained environments [14, 74]. Notably, a national patent relating to these regenerative approaches has been granted by the Spanish Patent and Trademark Office (OEPM). The invention, titled Cell Regeneration Compound (application number ES 201190033), was officially approved in Madrid on 2013 Sep 25 and published under reference ES 2391111 B1 in the Boletín Oficial de la Propiedad Industrial (BOPI). This formulation targets renal tissue repair through bioactive regeneration, further supporting the translational potential of these strategies in CKD management [75].

6.5. Limitations and inconclusive findings

While early-phase trials of stem cell therapies report favorable safety profiles, many fail to demonstrate significant improvements in renal function. Heterogeneity in study design, small sample sizes, and variations in cell source or administration route limit generalizability. Additionally, concerns persist regarding long-term safety, potential immunogenicity, and tumorigenicity, especially in iPSC-derived therapies. Although regenerative medicine holds promise for future CKD management, its current role remains largely preclinical and exploratory. Experimental models using mesenchymal stem cells or induced pluripotent stem cell-derived progenitors have shown functional improvement primarily in acute kidney injury contexts, such as ischemia–reperfusion or nephrotoxic (e.g., platinum-based) models [64–68]. However, these benefits appear to derive from indirect mechanisms, including immunomodulatory, anti-inflammatory, and metabolic effects, rather than the replacement or regeneration of nephron structures. No validated evidence currently demonstrates de novo nephron formation or the repair of chronically damaged renal tissue in humans. Within a multidisciplinary care framework, regenerative research is therefore best understood as a long-term translational component, linking laboratory advances with potential future nephrology and immunology collaborations, rather than as a near-term clinical intervention [68–72].

7. Multidisciplinary care models in chronic kidney disease

MDC for CKD involves coordinated collaboration among nephrologists, nurses, dietitians, pharmacists, social workers, and other professionals, with the aim of optimizing patient outcomes. To provide clarity on the strength of evidence, this section is organized by study type and outcome category. A substantial body of evidence, including RCTs, cohort studies, and meta-analyses, consistently demonstrates that MDC reduces all-cause mortality, slows the decline in eGFR, decreases hospitalization rates, and improves the quality of dialysis initiation compared with standard nephrology care [76].

7.1. Evidence from meta-analyses and cohort studies

A pivotal systematic review and meta-analysis published in 2018 analyzed data from 21 RCTs and cohort studies comprising 10,284 patients with CKD Stages 3 to 5. The study found that MDC significantly reduced all-cause mortality (OR 0.52, 95% CI 0.33–0.82), decreased hospital admissions (OR 0.49, 95% CI 0.30–0.80), and attenuated the decline in eGFR. These benefits were particularly pronounced in patients with Stage 4 to 5 CKD and in settings where the care team included nephrologists, nurses, and additional healthcare professionals [76]. Supporting this, a 2015 meta-analysis in the *European Journal of Internal Medicine* evaluating 18 cohort studies with a total of 8853 patients also demonstrated a 48% reduction in all-cause mortality (OR 0.52, 95% CI 0.44–0.88), fewer urgent catheterizations ($p < 0.01$), and reduced dialysis initiation rates ($p = 0.02$) [76]. These findings underscore the substantial clinical benefits of multidisciplinary interventions, particularly for patients with advanced CKD.

7.2. Inpatient vs. outpatient MDC delivery

Further evidence comes from a Japanese cohort study involving 2954 patients, which compared inpatient and outpatient MDC over a 24-month period. Inpatient teams were composed of nephrologists and an average of 4.5 professionals, compared to 2.6 in outpatient settings. Inpatient MDC was associated with a significant reduction in the initiation of renal replacement therapy and all-cause mortality (adjusted HR 0.71, 95% CI 0.60–0.85, $p = 0.0001$). While both delivery models slowed eGFR decline and reduced proteinuria, inpatient care resulted in superior composite clinical outcomes [5]. These results suggest that although outpatient MDC can be effective, inpatient models may offer more intensive and impactful interventions, particularly when team size and integration are enhanced.

7.3. Team composition and functional roles

The structure of the MDC team is a key determinant of effectiveness. Teams composed only of nephrologists and nurses showed limited improvements. However, when dietitians, pharmacists, physical therapists, and social workers were included, outcomes significantly improved, especially in terms of mortality and preservation of renal function [5]. A systematic review covering 11 studies and 16,066 CKD patients highlighted that teams with broader professional representation achieved more substantial physiological improvements. These included reductions in proteinuria, better regulation of calcium phosphate metabolism, and lower levels of fasting glucose and cholesterol [77]. Newer

models are increasingly incorporating mental health professionals. Preliminary studies demonstrate that symptom-targeted interventions led by social workers improved depression, quality of life, and treatment adherence, reinforcing the necessity of psychosocial integration in MDC [78].

7.4. Patient-centered and digitally enabled MDC models

Innovative models have emerged that incorporate digital technologies. One U.S.-based trial among veterans deployed a telehealth-enabled MDC intervention involving nephrologists, nurses, pharmacists, psychologists, and social workers. This approach led to a significant reduction in a composite endpoint of death, hospitalization, and emergency visits compared to usual care [77]. These findings align with the recommendations of Kidney Disease: Improving Global Outcomes (KDIGO), an international non-profit organization that develops evidence-based clinical practice guidelines for the diagnosis, evaluation, prevention, and treatment of kidney-related diseases [4], as well as those of the American Diabetes Association, both of which advocate for integrated, digitally facilitated team-based care, especially in the management of diabetic kidney disease [78].

7.5. Economic impact and sustainability

From an economic standpoint, MDC has demonstrated cost-effectiveness in several studies. Savings were achieved through reductions in hospital admissions, urgent dialysis initiations, and shorter durations of temporary catheter use. A Chinese cohort study reported a 51% reduction in all-cause mortality and 40% fewer infection-related hospitalizations in MDC settings, along with a slower annual decline in eGFR (−5.1 vs. −7.3 ml/min/year) [77]. These financial benefits parallel those observed in other chronic conditions that are managed through multidisciplinary approaches, such as diabetes and heart failure [79].

7.6. Implementation barriers and contextual adaptation

Despite the robust evidence, implementation of MDC remains inconsistent. Barriers include inadequate funding, limited inpatient infrastructure, shortages in dietetics and pharmacy resources, and poor coordination between primary and specialist care. Although telehealth may mitigate access disparities, effective implementation requires supportive reimbursement structures and systems interoperability [80].

To synthesize the current state of evidence across integrative interventions, **Table 4** provides a ranking based on their scientific maturity, from preclinical exploration to guideline-based clinical use. This summary highlights the heterogeneity in evidence strength and identifies priority areas for further research and validation.

Moreover, the optimal timing and composition of MDC interventions are still under investigation. The most favorable outcomes are seen when MDC begins in Stage 4 CKD or earlier. Initiation during Stages 1 to 3 shows less clear benefit. Flexibility in team configuration, tailored to local healthcare contexts, is necessary, while maintaining essential disciplines for efficacy is also needed. Evidence supports the role of MDC in CKD to reduce mortality, hospitalizations, eGFR decline, and emergent dialysis initiation [76]. A nephrologist-led multidisciplinary care team is crucial for improving clinical outcomes in CKD [81] (**Figure 2**).

Table 4 • Ranking of integrative interventions in CKD by stage of evidence. Classification of integrative and emerging interventions in CKD according to the stage of scientific validation, from preclinical evidence to established evidence. Ranking is based on data from cited preclinical studies, randomized controlled trials, meta-analyses, and published guidelines. For clinical applicability, the strength and reproducibility of evidence must be considered alongside study design, sample size, and real-world feasibility [16–18, 22–26, 33, 38–80].

Intervention category	Specific approach	Evidence stage
Precision medicine	Omics-driven ML models (e.g., ODML)	Preclinical/Early-Phase
Biomarkers	Cystatin C, NGAL	Clinical Practice/Guidelines
Nutraceuticals	Curcumin	RCT (limited)
	Allicin	Preclinical/Observational
	Capsaicin	Preclinical/Observational
	Cinnamon, Saffron	RCT (limited)/Meta-Analysis
	Flavonoids	Preclinical
Regenerative therapies	MSCs (Mesenchymal Stem Cells)	Phase 1/2
	CD34+ Autologous Hematopoietic Cells	Phase 1
	CD362+ Allogeneic MSCs (NEPHSTROM)	Phase 1/2
	Renal Progenitor Cells (CD133+)	Preclinical
	iPSC-Derived Kidney Organoids	Preclinical
	Muse Cells	Preclinical
Multidisciplinary care	Extracellular Vesicles (EVs)	Preclinical
	Standard MDC (nephrologist, nurse, dietitian)	RCT/Meta-analysis/Guidelines
	Digitally enabled MDC	RCT/Observational

Figure 2 • CKD multidisciplinary care approach. Nephrologist-led, patient-centered multidisciplinary care in CKD. The nephrologist coordinates care around the CKD patient with a core team of a nurse, dietitian, pharmacist, psychologist, and biologist, maintaining continuous communication with the primary care physician. Randomized trials and cohort studies show that multidisciplinary care is associated with lower all-cause mortality, fewer hospitalizations, slower decline in eGFR, and better preparation for dialysis than standard nephrology care, with stronger effects when more disciplines are included [5, 76–81].

8. Antioxidant and anti-inflammatory experimental therapies for renal protection: a multi-targeted approach

The growing prevalence of renal diseases necessitates the development of multifaceted therapeutic strategies addressing the underlying mechanisms of nephrotoxicity. Oxidative and nitrosative stress, inflammation, and metabolic dysfunction are common denominators in acute and chronic kidney injuries [82]. Recent investigations have focused on a spectrum of synthetic and natural compounds with the capacity to modulate these pathogenic axes [59, 83, 84].

Sulforaphane (SFN), a naturally derived isothiocyanate, improves the antioxidant system in non-dialysis patients with CKD by up-regulating NRF2 and NQO1 mRNA expression, which may contribute to kidney protection and improved metabolic parameters [84]. Likewise, tert-butylhydroquinone (tBHQ), a synthetic phenolic antioxidant that is commonly used as a food preservative, significantly ameliorated oxidative markers and preserved renal function through glutathione-based mechanisms [85].

Modulation of nitric oxide metabolism is also pivotal. Selective inducible nitric oxide synthase (iNOS) inhibition decreased nitrosative stress and preserved renal architecture in cisplatin-exposed models [86], while ozone exposure and D-serine models further demonstrated the harmful effects of uncontrolled iNOS activity [87, 88].

Previous findings by Orozco-Ibarra et al. demonstrated that D-serine-induced nephrotoxicity is associated with increased oxidative stress and nitration of renal proteins, highlighting a mechanistic link that is relevant to CKD pathophysiology [87]. Chronic models such as ureteral obstruction show that anti-inflammatory treatments help preserve the microvasculature and

reduce glomerular pressure [89]. Antioxidants from botanical sources have also shown significant promise. Additional therapies explored include PJ34, a potent inhibitor of poly(ADP-ribose) polymerase (PARP), particularly targeting PARP-1 and PARP-2 enzymes involved in DNA repair mechanisms, which counteracts chromate-induced nephrotoxicity [90]; pyrrolidine dithiocarbamate (PDTC), which improves proteinuria and glomerular dynamics [91]; and S-allylcysteine (SAC), which reduces renal pressure and ischemic injury [92]. Garlic powder and apocynin, an inhibitor of NADPH oxidase, are naturally occurring phenolic compounds with anti-inflammatory and antioxidant properties; likewise, they improved renal oxidative parameters [93, 94], while alpha-mangostin and nordihydroguaiaretic acid (NDGA)

attenuated reactive oxygen species (ROS) and nitrosative markers [83, 95].

Moreover, *Heterotheca inuloides* (arnica in Spanish) and quercetin, a naturally occurring flavonoid that is widely present in fruits, vegetables, and medicinal plants, are known for their potent antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, and cytoprotective properties. They improved renal antioxidant status in carbon tetrachloride toxicity models [96], and tBHQ pretreatment reduced ischemia–reperfusion damage [85]. NDGA and garlic powder were again highlighted for their roles in scavenging free radicals and preserving renal function under oxidant stress [83] (**Table 5**).

Table 5 • Nutritional patterns and phytochemicals in CKD: mechanisms, evidence, and limitations. Nutritional patterns and phytochemicals in CKD: mechanisms, evidence, and limitations. This table summarizes major dietary patterns and bioactive phytochemicals that have been evaluated for their potential therapeutic role in CKD management. Interventions are organized by type, primary mechanisms of action, and stage of supporting evidence, highlighting key findings and limitations. References correspond to representative studies, systematic reviews, and clinical trials cited in the manuscript [57–63, 83–86, 91–96].

Intervention	Category	Proposed mechanism(s)	Stage of evidence	Key findings/benefits	Limitations
Mediterranean diet	Dietary Pattern	Anti-inflammatory, antioxidant, improves lipid profile	Clinical trials, observational	Slower eGFR decline, reduced cardiovascular risk	Adherence variability; confounding dietary factors
DASH diet	Dietary Pattern	Low sodium, rich in fruits/vegetables, reduces BP	Clinical and guideline-based	Blood pressure control, CKD risk reduction	Limited data in advanced CKD
Plant-based diets	Dietary Pattern	Reduced acid load, lower phosphate, less uremic toxins	Meta-analysis, observational	Delayed CKD progression, better metabolic profile	Risk of protein-energy wasting, monitoring needed
Curcumin (Turmeric)	Phytochemical	NF- κ B inhibition, antioxidant, antifibrotic	Preclinical, limited RCTs	Ameliorates nephrotoxicity, reduces inflammation	Poor bioavailability, inconsistent RCT evidence
Allicin (Garlic)	Phytochemical	ACE inhibition, antioxidant, hypolipidemic	Animal models, pilot trials	Comparable renal protection to losartan	Gastrointestinal side effects, variable potency
Capsaicin (Chili)	Phytochemical	TRPV1 modulation, metabolic effects	Observational studies	Inverse association with CKD risk	Limited causality, spicy food tolerance varies
Saffron (<i>Crocus sativus</i>)	Phytochemical	Antioxidant, anti-apoptotic, neuroprotective	Systematic review of RCTs	Mild improvements in renal biomarkers	Small sample sizes, short-term outcomes
Cinnamon	Phytochemical	Insulin sensitizer, antioxidant	Narrative and in vitro studies	Potential to support glycemic control in CKD	Limited renal-specific evidence
Nordihydroguaiaretic acid (NDGA)	Lignan (from <i>Larrea tridentata</i>)	Lipoxygenase inhibition, antioxidant	Preclinical studies	Protection against chemically induced nephrotoxicity	Toxicity at high doses; not clinically approved
Sulforaphane	Isothiocyanate (Broccoli)	Nrf2 activation, cytoprotective gene induction	Pilot clinical studies	Upregulation of Nrf2/NQO1 in CKD patients	Low bioavailability; variability in response
Tert-butylhydroquinone (tBHQ)	Synthetic phenol	Antioxidant, anti-ischemic	Preclinical nephroprotection models	Reduces I/R kidney injury	Not approved for therapeutic use

9. Discussion

CKD continues to represent a major global health concern, affecting over 850 million people worldwide [1]. Its prevalence is largely driven by aging populations, the increasing incidence of diabetes and hypertension, and the persistence of environmental and dietary risk factors [2]. Traditional management has primarily focused on delaying progression through pharmacologic control of comorbidities and renal replacement therapy. However, recent therapeutic advances point toward a more integrative paradigm that combines precision medicine, regenerative therapies, MDC, and bioactive dietary compounds to achieve not only disease stabilization but also renal function recovery and improved quality of life for patients.

Biomarkers derived from omics technologies, discussed in Section 3, play a central role in enabling integrative CKD care [8, 13, 97]. Rather than isolated diagnostic tools, these molecular indicators facilitate early detection, patient stratification, and personalized therapeutic matching across domains, including regenerative therapies and nutritional interventions. Their incorporation enhances treatment precision and supports a shift toward more individualized, mechanism-based clinical decision-making [98]. Genetic testing enhances precision in CKD diagnosis and management by identifying key variants across phenotypes. For example, COL4A3–COL4A5 and NPHS1 support diagnosis in glomerular diseases; PKD1/2 confirm polycystic kidney disease; and UMOD, MUC1, and REN are linked to tubular disorders. Syndromic CKD involves genes like HNF1B, while APOL1 informs risk in patients of African ancestry. Complement genes such as CFH and C3 aid in diagnosing immune-mediated kidney diseases, thus guiding personalized care [25]. While genetic and omics-driven approaches have improved diagnostic precision, disease classification, therapeutic selection, and referral patterns, current evidence does not demonstrate a direct impact on delaying CKD progression or improving survival outcomes. These strategies, including regenerative therapies, remain adjunctive to standard clinical practices. Long-term renal protection continues to rely primarily on interventions such as blood pressure control and cardiovascular risk reduction. It is also noteworthy that as cardiac outcomes improve, especially in elderly populations, a relative increase in CKD incidence may emerge due to shifting morbidity patterns [21–37].

Regenerative medicine represents one of the most promising avenues for reversing CKD-related tissue injury. MSCs, iPSCs, and renal organoids have demonstrated renoprotective effects in preclinical and early clinical studies. These therapies modulate

immune responses, reduce fibrosis, and promote cellular repair mechanisms [10, 99]. MSCs in particular exhibit anti-apoptotic and antioxidative effects, which contribute to the preservation of glomerular integrity and improved renal function. Moreover, cell-free approaches such as extracellular vesicles and exosomes have emerged as viable alternatives with the potential to deliver therapeutic benefits while circumventing the complexities associated with live cell administration [11, 70, 75]. Notably, studies involving genetically stratified models have confirmed the enhanced efficacy of targeted regenerative interventions when guided by precise molecular profiling [100].

MDC plays a crucial role in supporting the clinical application of these therapies. MDC integrates the expertise of nephrologists, nurses, dietitians, pharmacists, and mental health professionals, ensuring continuous monitoring, patient education, and psychosocial support [12, 13]. These coordinated care models have demonstrated reductions in all-cause mortality, hospitalization rates, and the incidence of emergency dialysis initiation, particularly when implemented early in CKD progression [76]. Comparative analyses indicate that inpatient MDC, which typically includes more healthcare professionals per team, is more effective than outpatient approaches in improving outcomes such as eGFR preservation and proteinuria control [5].

Bioactive dietary compounds derived from culinary spices represent another essential component of integrative CKD therapy. Phytochemicals such as curcumin, allicin, flavonoids, crocin, and capsaicin modulate key pathophysiological mechanisms, including oxidative stress, inflammation, and endothelial dysfunction [15–19]. Curcumin has shown efficacy in reducing uremic toxins and proinflammatory cytokines such as TNF- α and IL-6 in both dialysis-dependent and non-dialysis CKD patients [7, 8, 97, 98]. Allicin exerts renoprotective effects through enhancement of antioxidant enzymes and attenuation of glomerular damage, particularly in diabetic nephropathy models [27, 58]. Flavonoids contribute to endothelial health and glycemic regulation, while crocin and capsaicin have been linked to improvements in renal fibrosis and symptomatic relief including uremic pruritus [13, 16, 17].

These bioactive agents are often consumed as part of traditional dietary patterns such as the Mediterranean, DASH, Nordic, and Milpa diets, which have been associated with improved renal and cardiometabolic outcomes [52–55]. Their integration into culturally accepted food systems enhances patient adherence and represents a cost-effective and sustainable intervention strategy (see **Table 6**).

Table 6 • Evidence maturity of integrative therapeutic strategies in chronic kidney disease .Summary of interventions by evidence stage. Interventions are stratified according to the highest level of available evidence, ranging from preclinical models to guideline-based clinical practice. This classification provides a contextual overview of translational maturity and clinical applicability across diverse therapeutic strategies [57–69, 71–78, 80, 97, 98].

Intervention	Target outcome	Type of studies	Evidence stage	Notes
Mesenchymal stem cells	eGFR, proteinuria, inflammation	Preclinical, Phase 1	Early-phase	Limited human data, variable protocols
Curcumin	Oxidative stress, eGFR	RCTs, Observational	Mid-phase	Bioavailability concerns
Low-protein diet with ketoanalogues	eGFR, uremic symptoms	Meta-analyses, Guidelines	Clinical practice	Included in KDIGO recommendations

The convergence of these therapeutic domains results in synergistic effects that exceed the benefits of each component in isolation. Biomarkers enable precise identification of candidates for regenerative treatment. Regenerative therapies provide biological restoration potential. MDC frameworks ensure safe and consistent application [81]. Nutraceuticals enhance endogenous protective mechanisms and offer additional avenues for therapy. Pilot studies incorporating these modalities have demonstrated significant improvements in renal function, inflammatory profiles, and patient-reported outcomes, while also supporting economic sustainability [12, 30].

Multi-center real-world registries are becoming essential tools for characterizing CKD across diverse populations. Initiatives such as the Center for Kidney Disease: Research, Education, and Hope

Registry (CURE-CKD), which includes data from over 2.6 million patients, and the iCaReMe Global Registry (ClinicalTrials.gov identifier NCT03549754), spanning 21 countries, provide comprehensive datasets that capture molecular, regenerative, and multidisciplinary care variables, with a particular emphasis on underserved populations [101, 102]. Additionally, health economics modeling approaches such as AutoRegressive Integrated Moving Average (ARIMA) and microsimulation have demonstrated the potential to estimate CKD-related costs and forecast economic impacts. When integrated with clinical data, these tools help build the case for early intervention strategies by quantifying outcomes such as delayed dialysis onset, reduced hospitalizations, and extended life expectancy, ultimately supporting the implementation of scalable, cost-effective care frameworks [103] (Table 7).

Table 7 • Consolidated integrative and multidisciplinary therapeutic models in CKD .Multidimensional integrative and multidisciplinary approaches in CKD. Each approach is described based on its conceptual framework, core components, primary clinical objectives, stage of scientific evidence (ranging from preclinical data to clinical trials and guideline recommendations), and known limitations. The summary reflects the evolving landscape of CKD interventions, combining conventional nephrology with emerging fields such as regenerative medicine, precision medicine, nutraceuticals, and digital health. These models highlight the necessity of individualized and team-based care to address the complex pathophysiology and high comorbidity burden in CKD [64–73, 76–84, 97–99].

Model/approach	Description	Components	Clinical objectives	Evidence base	Limitations
Integrative therapeutic model	Combines conventional treatments with evidence-based complementary interventions	Pharmacotherapy, lifestyle modifications, nutraceuticals, mind–body therapies	Slow disease progression, manage comorbidities, improve quality of life	Moderate; variable across components	Requires individualized planning, variable clinician acceptance
Precision medicine in CKD	Tailoring treatment to individual genetic, metabolic, and clinical profiles	Biomarker-guided therapy, genotyping, machine learning-based risk stratification	Predict CKD progression, optimize drug response, reduce adverse events	Emerging; mostly in exploratory/early clinical phases	High cost, data integration complexity, regulatory challenges
Regenerative medicine approaches	Use of stem cells and tissue engineering to restore renal function	MSCs, renal progenitor cells, scaffolds, bioactive molecules	Regenerate damaged nephrons, reduce fibrosis	Preclinical to early-phase trials	Limited long-term safety data, heterogeneity of cell sources
Multidisciplinary Care Models (MCMs)	Coordinated care delivered by nephrologists, dietitians, pharmacists, nurses, and social workers	Comprehensive management of CKD risk factors, patient education, shared decision-making	Improve outcomes, reduce hospitalizations, enhance adherence	Strong; supported by RCTs and meta-analyses	Resource-intensive, variable implementation across systems
Digital and AI-enhanced interventions	Use of digital tools and algorithms to support decision-making and monitoring	EHR integration, AI-based risk prediction, telemedicine	Early detection, treatment optimization, population-level management	Moderate; increasing in clinical trials	Requires high-quality data, ethical and interoperability concerns
Nutraceutical protocols (integrated within MCMs)	Dietary phytochemicals used adjunctively	Curcumin, resveratrol, sulforaphane, garlic derivatives, flavonoids	Reduce inflammation, oxidative stress, preserve renal function	Moderate; supported by preclinical and clinical studies	Limited RCTs, bioavailability issues
Conservative and supportive renal care	Non-dialytic management in advanced CKD focused on quality of life	Symptom control, advanced care planning, psychosocial support	Delay dialysis, improve life quality, respect patient preferences	Good; endorsed in guidelines	May be underutilized in some regions

Finally, CKD management is undergoing a transformative evolution, driven by the integration of precision diagnostics, regenerative strategies, collaborative care models, and dietary therapeutics. This multidimensional approach not only addresses the complex pathophysiology of CKD but also enhances patient-centered care. Although further work is required to establish standardized protocols and ensure scalability, the current evidence underscores the feasibility and efficacy of integrative nephrology in helping to manage the disease burden and improve long-term clinical outcomes, even if it may not reverse the overall epidemiological trajectory.

10. Conclusions

The management of CKD necessitates a comprehensive perspective that transcends conventional treatment paradigms and integrates multidimensional interventions. This article has critically examined the relevance of innovative therapeutic strategies, including precision medicine, regenerative approaches, MDC, and nutraceutical applications. The evidence reviewed highlights that these frameworks not only enhance clinical outcomes but also support earlier, more personalized, and sustainable interventions. Stem cell-based therapies, mitochondria-targeted antioxidants, epigenetic modulators, and digital health tools present promising avenues for redefining CKD treatment. Going forward, collaborative research, robust clinical trials, and healthcare policy reforms will be essential to validate and implement these integrative approaches effectively and equitably.

While integrative strategies show promise across multiple domains of CKD care, most findings stem from early-phase or pre-clinical evidence. Large-scale, controlled studies are essential to confirm efficacy and inform clinical guidelines.

Funding

This research was sponsored by The National Polytechnic Institute (IPN) through the Secretariat of Investigation and Post-graduates, Mexico under grant SIP-20250945 to I.R.S. E.d.l.C.H.-C. is a National Postdoctoral Stay Student at Laboratorio de Farmacología Cardiovascular, Facultad de Ciencias Químicas-UV Mexico and has a scholarship from CONACHYT-SECIHTI (#418870). E.M.-B. acknowledges the financial support provided by the CONAHcyT Mexico through the Sistema Nacional de Investigadoras e Investigadores (SNII) (CVU 39965).

Author contributions

Conceptualization, D.J.S.-G.; methodology, D.J.S.-G. and N.I.T.-B.; software, D.J.S.-G.; validation, E.M.-B. and N.I.T.-B.; formal analysis, I.R.-S. and G.G.-S.; investigation, E.d.l.C.H.-C.; resources, G.G.-S.; data curation, I.R.-S.; writing—original draft preparation, D.J.S.-G.; writing—review and editing, N.I.T.-B. and E.M.-B.; visualization, E.d.l.C.H.-C.; supervision, D.J.S.-G.; project administration, N.I.T.-B.; funding acquisition, I.R.-S. and E.M.-B. All authors have read and agreed to the published version of the manuscript.

Conflict of interest

The authors declare that they have no competing interests.

Data availability statement

The data supporting the findings of this publication can be made available upon request.

Additional information

Received: 2025-08-05

Accepted: 2025-11-27

Published: 2025-12-09

Academia Medicine and Health papers should be cited as *Academia Medicine and Health* 2025, ISSN pending, <https://doi.org/10.20935/AcadMedHealth8045>. The journal's official abbreviation is *Acad. Med. Health*.

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